

**UTILISATION OF FORENSIC AUDITING TECHNIQUES
FOR FRAUD DETECTION IN LARGE SCALE BUSINESS
ORGANISATIONS IN DELTA STATE, NIGERIA**

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Abstract:

This study on utilisation of forensic auditing investigation techniques for fraud detection in large scale business organisations in Delta State was necessitated by the growing incidence of frauds that are crippling businesses and socio-economic development of the state. Two research questions guided the study and two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Related literature to the study were reviewed. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study was 260 accounting staff. A sample size of 160 was selected for the study using simple random sampling technique. A four-point rating scale questionnaire developed by the researchers was used for data collection. Cronbach Alpha method was used to determine the reliability of the questionnaire and this yielded reliability coefficient values of 0.83 and 0.88 respectively for the sections with an overall reliability of 0.86. Data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to ascertain the homogeneity of the respondents while t-test and analysis of variance were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results showed that the accounting staff lowly utilised background investigation technique for fraud detection while investigative interview was moderately utilized. Furthermore, it was found that types and status of organization in NSE did not significantly influence their ratings on utilisation of background investigation and investigative interview for fraud detection. From the findings of the study, it was concluded that the accounting staff did not utilize forensic auditing investigation techniques for fraud detection in large-scale business

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organisations as required. Based on the findings, the researcher recommended among others, employees of large-scale business organisations should endeavour to support forensic auditors with relevant background information that could lead to fraud detection to ensure that the occurrence of fraud is minimized.

Keywords: forensic auditing, fraud and large-scale business organisation

1. Introduction

Large-scale businesses are the life wire of any nation because the rate at which an economy of a country generates and sustains annual increase in its Gross Domestic Products (GDP) depends, to a great extent, on the volume of activities of large-scale business organisations. According to the Nigerian Institute of Management (2009), a Large-Scale Business Organisation (LSBO) is an enterprise that has full-time labour force of more than 100 people and a total cost and working capital, less cost of land, of more than two hundred million naira. Large-scale business organisations constituted the main stabilizing force in Delta State economy in the 1970's and early 1980's. These organisations provided employment and income to Deltans. The number of people who worked for large-scale business organisations increased significantly with the introduction of the Indigenization Decree of 1977, which ensured the transfer of ownership and control of business organisations from foreigners to indigenes. This reduced foreign domination of these organisations and increased indigenous participation leading to the employment of Deltans at all levels of management (lower, middle and top levels) in these organisations in cities like Warri, Sapele, Asaba and Ughelli.

These businesses brought the then Bendel State to economic limelight as local and international investors saw the state as one of the "melting pots" for business activities in Nigeria. This was also facilitated by the availability of some infrastructural facilities – sea-port and good road network, through which these businesses imported materials, spare parts, work-in-progress and exported finished goods. The impacts of these organisations were felt in all the nooks and crannies of Nigeria as they helped in providing markets for the raw materials of small-scale producers, employment for the teeming population and revenue to the government.

The businesses improved local technology and raised the standard of living of the people through the provision of high quality goods, services and social amenities. Okandu, Azubuike, Onuaha, Chukwu and Emelike (2013) opined that it has become obvious that sustainable growth of business activities in any nation remains the key for unlocking the developmental potentials of the nation. Large-scale business organisations such as Delta Glass Plc, Eternit Ltd, Delta Steel Company Ltd and others flourished as they were patronized not only by Nigerians but also by other West African countries (Esene, 2010). Documented cases of fraud have shown that fraudulent practices pose a serious threat to the existence of LSBOs in Delta State in recent times.

In the Delta State business environment, fraud is so pervasive to the level that it has become the greatest bane on business growth and a clog in the wheel of economic development. There are various cases of fraud in Delta State. For example, \$182 million Halliburton energy service bribery scandal of 1994, Delta Steel company valued for \$1.5 billion which was sold for \$30 million (Ajibola, 2018). According to Esene (2010), many companies in Delta State have gone into liquidation due to mismanagement, inventory theft, and fraudulent reporting. The author listed Bendel Glass Factory, Delta Shrimp, Sparkling Breweries Ltd, Asaba Textile Mill, Super Ibru Breweries, Warri Bolting Company, Delta Boat Yard, among others as business entities that wound up due fraudulent activities.

The incidence of fraud and fraudulent activities in many LSBs in Delta State is alarming and unacceptable. Fraud has infested and invaded the fabrics of many businesses in the state leading to their liquidation. It has now become a normal way of life among employees at various levels (top, middle and lower) and is against global best practices. Fraud impairs the integrity, virtue or moral principle of employment and requires innovative methods such as forensic auditing to detect it. The occurrence of fraud in large scale business organisations in Nigeria and Delta State in particular has become rampant and persistent, as shown by several reported cases of bribery, embezzlement, cash theft, inventory theft, cheque tempering, payroll scheme, swindle, forgery and kickbacks in recent times. It is sad to say that no business is immune to fraud. Despite the fact that Nigerian government has set up two key anti-graft agencies: the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) and the Independent Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Commission (ICPC) to fight fraud and corruption in the country, significant change in their activities is yet to be seen as the business environment is still soaked in and characterized by fraud.

The problem of this study is that high level frauds are occurring persistently in Large Scale Business Organisations (LSBOs) in Delta State leading to down-sizing and complete winding-up of many such organisations due to financial insolvency. This results in loss of substantial investment by investors in the organisations, retrenchment of workers and increase in the level of unemployment with related vices such as armed robbery, kidnapping and youth restiveness. If this ugly trend is not urgently reversed, the state will lose its attraction to investors, standard of living will fall and Delta State will lag behind in socio-economic development. Fraudsters have continued to wax stronger in LSBOs in Delta State despite the application of traditional auditing practices. This poses a great problem and hence the need for wide utilisation of forensic auditing techniques to prevent or reduce frauds to the barest minimum. This made it imperative to conduct this study on utilisation of forensic auditing techniques for fraud detection in large scale business organisations in Delta state

2. Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to determine the level of utilisation of forensic auditing techniques for fraud detection in large scale business organisations in Delta state. Specifically, the study determined the level of utilisation of:

- 1) investigative interview for fraud detection in large-scale business organisations in Delta State;
- 2) background investigation for fraud detection in large-scale business organisations in Delta State.

2.1 Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- 1) What is the level of utilisation of investigative interview for fraud detection in large-scale business organisations in Delta State?
- 2) What is the level of utilisation of background investigation for fraud detection in large-scale business organisations in Delta State?

2.2 Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance.

- 1) There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of respondents from manufacturing, trading or service large-scale business organisations on the level of utilisation of interview for fraud detection.
- 2) Respondents do not differ significantly in their mean ratings on utilisation of interview for fraud detection based on the status of organisation in the Nigerian Stock Exchange.
- 3) There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of respondents from manufacturing, trading or service large-scale business organisations on the level of utilisation of background investigation for fraud detection.
- 4) Respondents do not differ significantly in their mean ratings on utilisation of background investigation for fraud detection based on the status of organisation in the Nigerian Stock Exchange.

2.3 Review of Literature

Forensic auditing investigation techniques are used to identify and gather evidence to prove, for example, how long a fraud has been carried out or how it was conducted and concealed by the perpetrators. Forensic auditing investigation techniques refer to the different inquiry methods adopted by auditors for the purpose of providing evidence of fraud against an individual in the court of law. Some of the techniques of forensic auditing investigation, according to Golden, Skalak and Clayton (2015) are data mining, background investigation and investigative interview.

An investigative interview is a conversation with a purpose. The purpose is to obtain information and, in some cases, an admission or confession. Golden, Skalak and

Clayton (2015) stated that there is no more compelling proof of a crime than a perpetrator's voluntary admission. In the later twentieth century, interviewing also emerged as a science, drawing on decades of psychological and sociological researches, including a great deal that had been learned from wartime interrogation. The interviewer must be ready to assume a variety of stances, modes or roles; can be sympathetic, logical, confrontational, accusatory or intimidating. Generally, in dealing with white-collar thieves, intimidation is less successful than the softer, sympathetic approaches, but that does not mean that a hard line is never appropriate. Golden and Dyer (2015) opined that auditors should approach inquiries related to fraud risk with special care in order to ensure that any underlying issue or unethical behaviour is uncovered. Golden and Dyer contended further that a forensic auditor without investigative skills may find fraud detection through interview to be particularly challenging. Effective interview is more than a well-executed analytical exercise: it requires great sensitivity to the subject's feelings and thoughts. By the same token, the American Institute of Chartered Public Accountants (2016) stated that inducing someone to make an admission is a difficult task indeed. To obtain admission in a fraud case in an organisation, various persons who are directly or indirectly involved could be interviewed. These include: current employees, suspects, suppliers, vendors, customers, relatives, accountants, stock brokers and significant others. For the purpose of fraud detection, there are two types of interview an auditor can conduct in an organisation. They include information-seeking interview and admission-seeking interview.

Okoye (2016) contended that to extract an admission of guilt, interviewers may need to make clear that they know the suspect is lying. People react to this accusation in different ways: some become emotional, breakdown, and confess everything; some respond aggressively; others grow silent. Experienced interviewers know they must first find ways to obtain an initial admission of wrong doing and then continue questioning to expand that admission into all pertinent areas. To be successful, the interviewer must be well versed in and comfortable with varieties of approaches as recommended by Golden and Dyer 2015. These include logical approach, silent approach, rationalisation approach and asking questions for which one knows the answer

A forensic auditor could also do a background investigation for the purpose of obtaining a firsthand evidence of fraud cases in a business organisation. Forensic auditors use background investigation for a variety of purposes. Sometimes, a background investigation is used to seek direct evidence of fraud, digging deeply into related party transactions. At other times, a background investigation can help to identify investigative leads, locate interviewees and perform asset search. Okoye and Gbegi (2013) averred that the enormous growth of information resources available on the internet and through commercial online services has revolutionised auditing investigation processes. Background information that can help to stem the tide of fraudulent practices could be sourced from government agencies, commercial media

database providers, local and international bodies among others. Data and information obtained from different sources need to be analysed.

Background investigation is a crucial activity in a bid to detect and prevent fraud in a business organisation. Jonny and Gregory (2015) observed that background investigation is used to seek direct evidence of a fraud. Relatedly, Chainese, Haimoff, Mcswain and Wiseman (2012) opined that background investigation can help to identify investigative leads, locate interviewees, and perform asset search. Songer (2016) posited that enormous growth in information resources available on the internet has revolutionised the investigative process. Songer further explained that in a matter of hours, a skilled forensic audit investigator can develop critical leads and make connections that may never be found through traditional investigation. Okoye and Okaro (2012) opined that forensic investigators need to identify data-bases or internet sites most likely to contain information relevant to the target of the investigation.

Background investigation could facilitate fraud detection and also act as a deterrent to criminally minded individuals who may want to engage in fraudulent activities in the future. The above review activities could help to expose related-party fraudulent activities, thereby nipping them in the bud. Relatedly, an analytic procedure could also be helpful in fraud detection in large scale business organisations. Alao (2016) investigated forensic auditing and financial fraud in Nigeria Deposit Money Banks. The results of the study showed that forensic audit has significant effect on financial fraud control in Nigerian Deposit Money Banks and that forensic audit report significantly enhances court adjudication on financial fraud. In addition, Ehioghiren and Atu (2016) carried out a study on forensic accounting and fraud management with evidence from Nigeria. The result of the study showed that forensic accounting significantly influences fraud control and management. Okunbor and Obaretin (2010) undertook a study on effectiveness of the application of forensic accounting services in Nigerian corporate organisations and came up with something different. Their study revealed that the application of forensic accounting services by corporate organisations in Nigeria is not effective in curbing fraudulent activities. Modugu and Anyaduba (2013) investigated forensic accounting and financial fraud in Nigeria adopting an empirical approach. The finding of the study indicated that there was significant agreement among stakeholders on the effectiveness of forensic accounting in fraud control, financial reporting and internal control quality.

3. Research Method

The descriptive survey design was adopted for this study. The study was conducted in Delta State. The population for the study comprises all the 268 accounting staff (manufacturing organisations – 108, trading organisations – 75 and service organisations – 85) in all the 30 large-scale business organisations in Delta State. The sample size of 160 (manufacturing organisations – 62, trading – 50, service – 48) was used for the study. This sample size was derived statistically using Taro Yamane

formulae. A structured questionnaire titled “Utilisation of Forensic Auditing Investigation Techniques for Fraud Detection Questionnaire (UFAITFDQ)” was used for data collection for the study. The instrument was developed by the researchers based on the research questions that guided the study. It contains 21 items in two sections: Sections A and B. Section A contains three items on the personal data of the respondents while section B was split into two clusters of B1 and B2. Section B is a four-point response scale of Highly Utilised (HU) – 4 points, Moderately Utilised (MU) – 3 points, Lowly Utilised (LU) – 2 points and Not Utilised (NU) – 1 point. The instrument was subjected to face-validity by three validators; one from Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. The internal consistency of the instrument was determined using Cronbach’s Alpha technique and a reliability coefficient of 0.85 was obtained. The questionnaire was administered on the respondents by the researchers. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and ascertain the closeness of the respondents’ means. Decision on the research questions were based on the cluster mean relative to the real limits of numbers shown below:

Table 1: Response Options Relative to Real Limit

Response Options	Values	Real Limit
Highly Utilised (HU)	4	3.50 – 4.00
Moderately Utilised (MU)	3	2.50 – 3.49
Lowly Utilised (LU)	2	1.50 – 2.49
Not Utilised (NU)	1	0.50 – 1.49

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and independent t-test were used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. A null hypothesis was rejected where the p-value was less than or equal to the alpha level of 0.05 otherwise it was not rejected.

4. Results

Research question 1: What is the level of utilisation of investigative interview for fraud detection in large-scale business organisations in Delta State?

Table 2: Respondents’ Mean Ratings on the Level of Utilisation of Investigative Interview for Fraud Detection in Large-scale Business Organisations in Delta State (N = 156)

S/N	Investigative Interview Techniques	Mean	SD	Remarks
1	Paying attention to non-verbal cues of fraud suspect	2.83	.87	MU
2	Interrogation of fraud suspects at the most suitable time	3.24	.75	MU
3	Records of conversation between the interviewer and the interviewee	3.13	.49	MU
4	Conduct of interview in a suitable environment	2.99	.79	MU
5	Asking of leading questions	2.56	.50	MU
6	Friendly posture during the interview process	2.67	.98	MU
7	Commendation of interviewee on his positive contributions in the organization	3.38	.61	MU
8	Asking some questions to which the interviewer already knows the answer	2.44	.71	LU

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9	Use of simple language in the interview process	3.00	.80	MU
10	Interview of different fraud suspects at different times	2.89	.78	MU
11	Use of probing questions	2.94	.91	MU
Cluster Mean		2.92		MU

Table 2 shows that 10 of the items have mean ratings between 2.56 and 3.38 meaning that they are moderately utilised while the remaining one item has mean score of 2.44 showing that it is lowly utilised. The cluster mean score of 2.92 shows that investigative interview is moderately utilised for fraud detection in large-scale business organisations in Delta State. The standard deviation for all the items is low and indicates that the respondents' views were not widespread.

Research question 2: What is the level of utilisation of background investigation for fraud detection in large-scale business organisations in Delta State?

Table 3: Respondents' Mean Ratings on the Level of utilisation of Background Investigation for Fraud Detection in Large-scale Business Organisations in Delta State (N = 156)

S/N	Background Investigation Techniques	Mean	SD	Remarks
1	Information from home page of business website	1.76	.43	LU
2	Information from public records	1.98	.70	LU
3	Information from private records	1.49	.62	NU
4	Inquiry of transaction with private companies of employees	2.01	1.33	LU
5	Investigation of transactions with relations of employees	1.92	.82	LU
6	Search of details of conflict among employees of the company	1.68	.75	LU
7	Search of transactions with parties lacking capacity	3.14	.99	MU
8	Search of transactions with employees' spouses	2.37	.93	LU
9	Search of transactions with employees' driver	1.98	.70	LU
10	Inquiry into transactions that deviate from business culture	2.72	1.15	MU
Cluster Mean		2.11		LU

Table 3 shows that two items have mean ratings of 3.14 and 2.72 meaning that they are moderately utilised while the remaining eight items have mean scores ranging from 1.49 – 2.37 showing that they are lowly utilised. The cluster mean score of 2.11 shows that background investigation is lowly utilised for fraud detection in large-scale business organisations in Delta State. The standard deviation range for all the items is low and indicates that the respondents' views were not dispersed.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of respondents from manufacturing, trading or service large-scale business organisations on the level of utilisation of interview for fraud detection.

Table 4: ANOVA Summary of the Difference in the Mean Ratings of Respondents from Manufacturing, Trading or Service Large-scale Business Organisations on the Level of Utilisation of Interview for Fraud Detection

Sources of Variations	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P-value	Decision
Between Groups	6.011	2	3.006	4.169	.054	NS
Within Groups	110.316	153	.721			
Total	116.327	155				

Table 4 shows that at .05 level of significance for 2 and 153 degrees of freedom, the P-value of .054 which is greater than the alpha level of .05 was obtained. This shows that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of respondents from manufacturing, trading or service large-scale business organisations on the level of utilisation of investigative interview for fraud detection. The null hypothesis was, therefore, not rejected.

Hypothesis 2: Respondents do not differ significantly in their mean ratings on utilisation of interview for fraud detection based on the status of organisation in the Nigerian Stock Exchange.

Table 5: t-test Analysis of the Difference in the Mean Ratings of Respondents on the Level of Utilisation of Investigative Interview for Fraud Detection Based on the Status of their Organisations in the Nigerian Stock Exchange

Status in NSE	N	SD	df	t-cal	P-value	Decision
Quoted X ₁	21	2.72	.87	.10592		
Unquoted X ₂	135	2.91	.86	.09130	-1.39	.168

Table 5 shows that the P-value of .168 is greater than the alpha level of .05 with the degree of freedom of 154. This means that respondents do not differed significantly in their mean ratings on utilisation of investigative interview for fraud detection based on the status of their organisations in the Nigerian Stock Exchange (quoted/unquoted). The null hypothesis was, therefore, not rejected.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of respondents from manufacturing, trading or service large-scale business organisations on the level of utilisation of background investigation for fraud detection.

Table 6: ANOVA Summary of the Difference in the Mean Ratings of Respondents from Manufacturing, Trading or Service Large-scale Business Organisations on the Level of Utilisation of Background Investigation for Fraud Detection

Sources of Variations	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P-value	Decision
Between Groups	122.029	2	61.015	114.75	.221	NS
Within Groups	81.561	153	.533			
Total	203.590	155				

Table 6 reveals that at .05 level of significance for 2 and 153 degrees of freedom, the P-value of .221 which is greater than the alpha level of .05 is obtained. This shows that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of respondents from manufacturing, trading or service large-scale business organisations on the level of utilisation of background investigation for fraud detection. The null hypothesis was, therefore, not rejected.

Hypothesis 4: Respondents do not differ significantly in their mean ratings on utilisation of background investigation for fraud detection based on the status of organisation in the Nigerian Stock Exchange.

Table 7: T-test Analysis of the Difference in the Mean Ratings of Respondents on the Level of Utilisation of Background Investigation for Fraud Detection Based on the Status of Their Organisations in the Nigerian Stock Exchange

Status in NSE	N	SD	df	t-cal	P-value	Decision	
Quoted X ₁	21	21.64	2.15	154	1.93	.055	NS
Unquoted X ₂	135	20.63	3.86				

Table 7 shows that the P-value of .055 at 154 degree of freedom is greater than the alpha level of .05. This means that respondents do not differed significantly in their mean ratings on utilisation of background investigation for fraud detection based on the status of their organisations in the Nigerian Stock Exchange (quoted/unquoted). The null hypothesis was, therefore not, rejected.

5. Summary of Findings

Findings of the study are summarized as follows:

- 1) Interview is moderately utilised for fraud detection in large-scale business organisations in Delta State.
- 2) Background investigation is lowly utilised for fraud detection in large-scale business organisations in Delta State.
- 3) There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of respondents from manufacturing, trading or service large-scale business organisations on the level of utilisation of interview for fraud detection.

- 4) Respondents do not differ significantly in their mean ratings on utilisation of interview for fraud detection based on the status of their organisations in the Nigerian Stock Exchange (quoted/unquoted).
- 5) There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of respondents from manufacturing, trading or service large-scale business organisations on the level of utilisation of background investigation for fraud detection.
- 6) Respondents do not differ significantly in their mean ratings on level of utilisation of background investigation for fraud detection based on the status of their organisations in the Nigerian Stock Exchange (quoted/unquoted).

6. Discussion

The findings indicated that investigative interview is moderately utilised for fraud detection in large-scale business organisations in Delta State. This finding is similar to the finding of Alao (2016) who found that forensic audit has significant effect on financial fraud control in Nigerian Deposit Money Banks and that audit report significantly enhance court adjudication on financial fraud detection. This shows that investigative interview can be helpful in uncovering fraudulent activities in a large-scale business organisation. Such an interview may extend beyond the employees of the organisations for the sole aim of getting confession or information that could lead to fraud detection.

The findings also showed that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of respondents from manufacturing, trading or service large-scale business organisations, quoted or unquoted on the level of utilisation of investigative interview for fraud detection in large-scale business organisations in Delta State. The findings are in line with the finding of Ehioghiren and Atu (2016) who found that forensic accounting significantly influences fraud control and management. Investigative interview as a technique in forensic auditing could be used to unearth material misstatement, fraudulent financial reporting and asset misappropriation in a business organisation.

The finding of the study reveals that background investigation is lowly utilised for fraud detection in large-scale business organisations in Delta State. This finding is related to the finding of Okunbor and Obaretin (2010) whose finding showed that the application of forensic accounting services by corporate organisations in Nigeria is not effective in curbing fraudulent activities. In Nigerian, the ethics of secrecy and confidentiality enshrined in work place could frustrate fraud detection efforts of organisations. In some cases, it could be taunting when trying to get information that could support fraud detection from public and private records due to bureaucracy. More often than not, the forensic auditor is seen as a watchdog and a witch-hunter such that, some employees who have committed or aided fraud will do everything possible to deny the auditor complete access to background information that could lead to fraud detection.

It is worth noting that the primary responsibility for the detection of fraud rests with those charged with governance of an entity and management. It is important that management with the oversight of those charged with governance, place a strong emphasis on fraud prevention, which may reduce opportunity for fraud to take place and persuade individuals not to commit fraud because of the likelihood of detection and punishment. This is in line with the tenets of the fraud box key model by Okoye and Onodi in 2014 that explained that corporate governance will help to lock the thinking of fraudsters in a box and reduce fraud occurrence to the barest minimum.

The findings further showed that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of respondents from manufacturing, trading or service large-scale business organisations, quoted or unquoted on the level of utilisation of anonymous communication for fraud detection in large-scale business organisations in Delta State. This finding is in line with the finding of Modugu and Anyanduba (2013) whose finding indicated that there is significant agreement among stakeholders on the effectiveness of forensic accounting in fraud control, financial reporting and internal control quality. The level of utilisation of anonymous communication need to be done with care to ensure that the identity of whistleblower is protected and information is used for the purpose for which it was given.

7. Conclusion

From the findings of the study, it was concluded that accounting staff did not utilise forensic auditing investigation techniques such as interview and background investigation for fraud detection in large-scale business organisations in Delta State as expected. As such, fraudulent activities like bribery, embezzlement, cash theft, inventory theft, cheque tempering, payroll scheme, swindle, forgery and kickbacks are causing incessant winding-up of large-scale business organisations in Delta State and these portend a no mean danger for socio-economic development of the state if not properly checked and nipped in the bud.

8. Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are therefore made:

- 1) Accounting staff of large scale business organisations should always avail themselves of any training opportunity on forensic interview technique provided by their organisations because that would help them to obtain admission and confession from fraudsters.
- 2) Employees of large-scale business organisations should endeavour to support forensic auditors with relevant background information that could lead to fraud detection to ensure that the occurrence of fraud is minimized to the barest minimum.

- 3) Shareholders in large scale business organisations should insist that the techniques used in the study and other forensic auditing techniques are adequately utilized by holding and management accountable for fraud occurrences.

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